

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP3.19

Workpackage 3

Responsible Partner: NVI (NO)

Contributing partners: NVI (NO), RKI (DE),
APHA (UK)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 36 months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP3.19 Information on the effect of different disinfectants on <i>Salmonella</i> in biofilm
Project Acronym	JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE
Author	Ane M. Osland (NVI), Lene K. Vestby (NVI), Claire Oastler (APHA), Emma Brooks (APHA), Becky Gosling (APHA), Mardjan Arvand (RKI), Katharina Konrat (RKI), Anja Richter (RKI).
Other contributors	All task partners: Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI), Robert Koch Institut (RKI), Animal and plant health agency (APHA)
Due month of the report	56
Actual submission month	56
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 25.08.2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Confidential until publication.....
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): via publication

BIOPIGEE

Information on the effect of different disinfectants on *Salmonella* in biofilm

Participating country

NO (NVI), DE (RKI), UK (APHA)

Background

Salmonellosis was the second most reported zoonosis in the EU in 2020, affecting more than 50,000 people (1). The causative agent of Salmonellosis is *Salmonella*, a bacterium frequently found in the intestines of healthy animals. *Salmonella* are known to form biofilms and in this state, the bacteria are more tolerant to disinfectants and cleaning routines compared to planktonic bacteria. Therefore, they may survive in the environment and cause infection in animals, food products and handlers.

Objective

There is currently no ISO standard method that takes into account *Salmonella* biofilms when assessing the efficacy of disinfectants. The objective of this work was to, using three biofilm models, evaluate the effect of two disinfectants against wild type (WT) *Salmonella* strains and at the same time to compare the three test methods.

Methods

To assess the efficacy of disinfectants on WT *Salmonella*, five wild- type strains of *S. Typhimurium* and one *S. Derby* strain with weak, moderate and strong levels of known biofilm production were studied (Table 1). These isolates were selected from panel of 15 *S. Derby* isolates and 35 *S. Typhimurium* (including monophasic variants) collected from finishers and/or sow/gilt pig faeces on indoor finishing, fattening or breeding farms in the United Kingdom from 2006 to 2019, and screened for biofilm formation.

Strain	Biofilm classification	Colony morphology
L01107-08 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT193	Strong	RDAR
S04187-13 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> U288	Strong	RDAR
S01829-11 <i>S. Derby</i>	Moderate	RDAR
S00750-19 Monophasic <i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT193	Moderate	RDAR
S00534-18 Monophasic <i>S. Typhimurium</i> DT193	Moderate	RDAR
L01764-06 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> U302	Weak	SAW

Table 1. The strains included in the study, their biofilm classification and their colony morphology. Biofilm formation was based on crystal violet binding of biofilms grown after 48h aerobic incubation at 20 ±1°C in 96 well plates as described by Schonewille *et al.*, 2012 (2). Biofilm classification was assessed according to Stepanović, *et al* 2004 (3). Colony morphology was assessed according to (4) indicating the presence (RDAR) or absence (SAW) of matrix components curli and cellulose, respectively, in colony biofilms grown on Congo red containing agar.

Disinfectants: The following disinfectants at different concentrations were tested on 2-day-old biofilms [cultured in Luria Bertani broth (LB) without NaCl] at 20°±1° C:

A) Peracetic acid (Lerasept spezial®), exposure time 10 min, neutralization with 1.65 % sodium sulfite in 0.1M Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS, pH 7)

B) Glutaraldehyde (Protectol®), exposure time 30 min, neutralization with 20 g/L glycine, 10 g/L tween 80 in 0.25M PBS.

The efficacy of each disinfectant was measured by assessing the recoverable viable colony forming units (CFU). Disinfection was defined as $\geq 5 \log_{10}$ reduction in recoverable average CFU in accordance with European standards.

The following disinfection testing methods on biofilms were applied:

1) **Bead-based biofilm model by RKI**

Biofilms were cultivated on 4 mm porous glass beads (Sinterglas Pellets, ROBU Glasfilter-Geräte GmbH) in 24-well microplates (one bead per well), each well containing 1 mL of 10^5 CFU/mL bacterial inoculum. Plates were incubated on an orbital shaker at 100 rpm at 20 °C for 48 h for biofilm cultivation. Thereafter, each bead was carefully dipped in 2 mL sterile H₂O and placed in a 2 mL microcentrifuge tube containing 0.2 mL disinfectant. After incubation for the defined exposure time (see above), 1.8 mL of the neutralizing broth was added to each microcentrifuge tube. Subsequently, bacteria were sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 10 min to detach the biofilm from the bead surface and quantified by serial dilution. All dilution steps were done in neutralizing agent. The controls were treated with hard water instead of disinfectant. All experiments were performed three times with two technical replicates each.

2) **Biofilm model by NVI**

To create a working culture in broth bacterial cultures on blood agar were transferred to 5 mL LB and the optical density (OD) was measured and adjusted to 1 McFarland. Then 0.5 mL of each bacterial suspension was added to 10 mL of LB without NaCl together with an autoclaved stainless-steel coupon of 75x24x1 mm (Stainless steel AISI304, 2B Olaf Johansens Eftf. A/S, Oslo, Norway) and incubated at 20 °C for 48 h. Thereafter, the coupon was rinsed 3x in 40 mL sterile saline and transferred to a tube with 10 mL of disinfectant (or saline for controls) for the applicable exposure time (see above). The coupon was then moved to a tube with appropriate neutralization broth before it was rinsed 3x again and added to a tube containing glass beads and 5 mL saline. Here, visible biofilm was scraped off both sides of the coupon by using an 18 cm long cell scraper with a blade of 1.8 cm. The coupon was discarded before the tube was vortexed for one minute. An aliquot of 0.2 mL from each tube was added to wells in a microtiter plate. Serial dilutions were performed before plating 5 μ L on blood agar which were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h to determine the viable CFU count. All experiments were performed three times with two technical replicates each.

3) **Biofilm model by APHA**

Salmonella isolates were inoculated into LB without NaCl and the bacterial suspension adjusted to 1 McFarland. To each well in a 12-well microplate 1.5 mL of this bacterial suspension was added along with one sterile Polyvinyl carbonate (PVC) coupon (10x20x0.6 mm; Pegen industries Inc, Ontario, Canada). Coupons were placed in the well so that only the bottom half of the coupon was submerged in the bacterial suspension. Microtiter plates underwent static aerobic incubation for 48 h at 20 \pm 1°C. After incubation, each coupon was washed three times, with light agitation, in 9 mL sterile saline and left to dry at room temperature. Coupons were submerged in either 10 mL disinfectant or 10 mL hard water for the specified exposure time (see above) before being transferred to 10 mL of the appropriate neutralizer broth. After a minimum of 5 min neutralization time, coupons were transferred to 5 mL sterile saline with glass beads and shaken at the lowest speed on a vortex-mixer for 2 min, before a further 5 mL of saline was added. Serial dilutions were performed and 100 μ L spread-plated on sheep blood agar plates to allow for enumeration of viable bacteria (CFU counts), following overnight incubation at 37 \pm 1°C. Experiments were performed with two technical replicates and three biological replicates.

Results

Among all three laboratories the concentrations used to attain $\geq 5 \log_{10}$ reduction in CFU for biofilms of the five WT *Salmonella* strains with Peracetic acid ranged between 0.001% and 0.1%. The concentrations to accomplish the same reduction in CFU with Glutaraldehyde ranged between 0.1% and 1% (see Fig. 1). However, in the APHA biofilm model, insufficient ($<6 \log_{10}$ CFU/coupon) amount of biofilm could not be formed for strain L01764-06, to allow for disinfectant testing and so this strain was excluded from their tests.

Fig. 1: Darkest color is 0%, followed by columns 0,01%, 0,05%, 0,1%, 0,5% and 1 %, respectively.

No visible column indicates no growth.

All strains are tested on all concentrations except 1% GA or strain L01764-06 which are not included by APHA.

Error bars shows standard error of the mean (SEM).

Previously, the three biofilm assays were used to test the efficacy of disinfectants on two *Salmonella* reference strains by two technicians. In addition, one laboratory tested the efficacy of disinfectants on planktonic reference strains. The results are formerly reported in D-JRP#-WP3.10.

Conclusion

According to our study, there is a need of at least 0.1% PAA for 10 minutes and at least 1% GA for 30 minutes to successfully disinfect *Salmonella* in biofilm i.e. cause a $\geq 5 \log_{10}$ reduction in CFU. Although differences in the disinfectant concentration required to achieve successful disinfection varied between the three test methods. This displays the need to use a higher concentration of disinfectants against bacteria in biofilm compared to planktonic bacteria and this applies to all three different materials (PVC coupons, stainless steel coupons and glass beads) and on WT *Salmonella* strains, as well as *Salmonella* reference strains.

Future work

As variations were observed between established laboratory models and the fact that a higher concentration is required to cause a $\geq 5 \log_{10}$ reduction in CFU bacteria in biofilm compared to that of planktonic bacteria, it is necessary to develop an ISO standard for testing the effect of disinfectants on

Salmonella in biofilm. This may result in changes in recommended concentrations and/or exposure times for disinfectants in practical settings, e.g. in swine production industry.

References:

EFSA and ECDC (European Food Safety Authority and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), 2021. The European Union One Health 2020 Zoonoses Report. *EFSA Journal* 2021;19(12):6971, 324 pp.<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6971>

Schonewille, E., Nesse, L. L., Hauck, R., Windhorst, D., Hafez, H. M., & Vestby, L. K. (2012). Biofilm building capacity of *Salmonella enterica* strains from the poultry farm environment. *FEMS immunology and medical microbiology*, 65(2), 360–365. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-695X.2012.00966.x>

Stepanović, S., Cirković, I., Ranin, L., & Svabić-Vlahović, M. (2004). Biofilm formation by *Salmonella* spp. and *Listeria monocytogenes* on plastic surface. *Letters in applied microbiology*, 38(5), 428–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-765X.2004.01513.x>

ČABARKAPA, I., ŠKRINJAR, M., LEVIĆ, J., KOKIĆ, B., BLAGOJEV, N., MILANOV, D. & SUVAJDŽIĆ, L. (2015). Biofilm forming ability of *Salmonella Enteritidis* in vitro. *Acta Vet Beogr*, 65, 371-389

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.